

Implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland

Version 2.0 July 2025

Coordinated by

HEAnet

Please cite as: Sabatino, R., O'Neill, J., Dowling, L., Burbidge, C., Brown, W., Collins, D., Culhane, A., Doran, M., Farrell, G., Golden, D., Kannan, V., Moran, R. P., Neff, F., Whelan, L., & Wrynn, S. (2025). Implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland - Version 2 July 2025. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16266119>

Authors

- **Roberto Sabatino (coordination lead)**, Research Engagement Officer, HEAnet
- **William Brown**, Senior System Administrator (Research IT), Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
- **Chris Burbidge**, Project Manager (Research IT) & iCrag, University College Dublin
- **Diarmuid Collins**, Senior Systems Administrator, School of Computing, Dublin City University
- **Aedín Culhane**, Professor of Cancer Genomics, School of Medicine, Director Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre, Head of Node for Elixir Ireland, University of Limerick
- **Michelle Doran**, National Open Research Coordinator, National Open Research Forum
- **Lindsay Dowling**, Open Research Support Unit Lead, Research & Innovation, Technological University Dublin
- **Gavin Farrell**, ELIXIR Ireland Node Coordinator, University of Limerick
- **Darach Golden**, Research IT Manager, IT services, Trinity College Dublin
- **Venkatesh Kannan**, Associate Director (Solutions R&D), Irish Centre for High End Computing
- **Ruth Moran**, Graduate Education and Research Integrity Officer, Atlantic Technological University
- **Flaithrí Neff**, Academic & Researcher, Technological University of the Shannon
- **Jenny O'Neill**, Research Engagement Officer, HEAnet
- **Laura Whelan**, Lecturer, FutureNeuro, Research Ireland Centre, School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences, RCSI University of Medicine and Health Sciences
- **Shirley Wrynn**, Research Integration Project Manager, Atlantic Technological University

Contributors

Christine Brennan, Research Strategy & Policy Manager, UL; **Brendan Curran**, APC Microbiome, UCC; **Edie Davis**, Research Policy programme Officer, Research Ireland; **John Donovan**, Head of Research Support Services, TU Dublin; **Dan Eames**, Senior Digital Design Advisor, National Disability Authority; **Abdoulie Faal**, iCrag Data Manager, UCD; **Sarah Gleeson**, iCrag Director, UCD; **Lisa Griffith**, Director, Digital Repository of Ireland; **Paul Hynds**, Pre-Award Lead, TU Dublin; **Cillian Joy**, Head of Open & Digital Research, Library, University of Galway; **Dan Kilper**, Director Connect Centre, TCD; **Brendan Kenna**, iCrag IT Manager, UCD; **Beth Knazook**, Research Data Project Manager, Digital Repository of Ireland; **Gavin Lawler**, Programme Manager, Research and Innovation Infrastructures, HRB; **Dave Lewis**, Associate Professor School of Computer Science, TCD; **Tania Marsh**, Research Integration Project Manager, TUS; **Cormac McKenna**, Head of Technical Operations, ADAPT; **Declan McKibben**, Executive Director Commercialisation, ADAPT; **Michael Meagher**, Director Open Ireland Network, UL; **Joan Murphy**, National Manager, DARIAH-IE, Trinity Long Room Hub, TCD; **Barry O'Sullivan**, IT Operations Manager, UCC; **Martina Prendergast**, Research Officer, UL, LERO; **Niall Reenan**, School of Earth Sciences IT Manager, UCD; **John Ronan**, Walton Institute, SETU; **Winnie Ryan**, Senior Project Manager, UCD; **Sebastian Schmidt**, APC Microbiome, UCC; **Michael Scriney**, Assistant Professor, Engineering & Computing, DCU; **Armin Straube**, Research Data Manager, UL; **Koen Torremans**, Assistant Professor School of Earth Sciences, UCD.

*Thanks also to **Sara Garavelli**, Strategic European Engagement and Coordination Development Manager, CSC - IT Center for Science in Finland for contributing an overview of EOSC-Finland.*

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	6
2. Vision.....	10
3. Requirements for the EOSC Ireland node	14
4. National Readiness for EOSC Ireland.....	21
5. SWOT Analysis.....	25
6. Recommended Actions	28
7. Motivation & Opportunities.....	31
8. Conclusion.....	37
Appendix 1: CSA Budget.....	39
Appendix 2: Federation build-up and expected costs of an EOSC node	44
Appendix 3: National, Institutional and Thematic Infrastructures and Services	46
Appendix 4: Broader National Context	54
Appendix 5: A Usage Case for EOSC.....	58
Appendix 6: Other EOSC national nodes.....	61
Glossary of Terms.....	63

Executive Summary

This paper proposes the development of a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation national node¹ for Ireland: EOSC Ireland.

EOSC Ireland will be a digital platform that connects researchers and research infrastructures across Ireland to the European-wide EOSC Federation, a stated EU priority action to accelerate open science across Europe. It will allow researchers and their stakeholders to share, access and provide data, tools, and applications, making national and international collaboration and innovation easier. EOSC Ireland will therefore serve as the digital fabric that seamlessly weaves together data, compute resources, and research workflows. As such it will provide a focus for policy around research funding and research data.

To achieve this, EOSC Ireland must establish essential functions such as resource catalogue and registry services, identity management, service monitoring and accounting, order management, helpdesk and service management, and application and data-governance workflow management - functions that not only support research workflows but also help reduce the administrative burden on researchers by aligning with institutional data governance policies and public research values.

It is crucial to onboard national HPC and data storage resources, institutional compute and storage services, research data repositories, and thematic research infrastructures to create a minimum viable product (MVP) that is useful to researchers - not only for national projects, but also to enable meaningful participation in European research initiatives. EOSC Ireland can provide the foundation that allows Ireland's researchers to actively engage with, and contribute to, large-scale thematic research infrastructures. This is especially important in areas where Ireland's involvement has been limited, not due to a lack of research excellence, but often due to the absence of visible, scalable infrastructure.

Furthermore, the EOSC Ireland node must be enrolled as part of the EOSC Federation, extending the scope of Ireland's Open Research development to a global context. Achieving this requires that the host of the EOSC Ireland node, responsible for the running and ongoing development of EOSC Ireland, be a legal entity, with a sustainable funding model.

Implementing EOSC in Ireland through a dedicated national node will directly advance Ireland's core policy and strategic goals:

- **Leadership in Open Research:** *Impact 2030*² positions Ireland as a global frontrunner in Open Research, innovation, and skills development. EOSC Ireland operationalises this ambition.
- **ERA Priority Action:** Ireland has committed to Action 1 of the European Research Area (ERA) priorities³ - Open Science. EOSC Ireland delivers on this commitment.

¹ An EOSC Node is a national or institutional access point to the European Open Science Cloud, enabling researchers to access and share data, tools, and services in a federated environment.

² [Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy](#)

³ [ERA Actions \(2025-2027\)](#)

- **National Open Research Forum (NORF):** EOSC Ireland addresses key actions in the NORF National Action Plan⁴, including infrastructure mapping, gap analysis, and integration with EOSC.
- **Open Data Alignment:** Ireland's Open Data Strategy (2023–2027)⁵ aligns with EOSC's principles, ensuring coherence between public sector and research data ecosystems.
- **Digital Transformation:** EOSC Ireland will be a cornerstone of Ireland's digital research infrastructure - enabling secure data access, reproducibility, responsible AI, and robust data governance.

As Ireland prepares to assume the EU Presidency in the latter half of 2026, active engagement with the EOSC Federation will serve as a strategic demonstration of leadership in shaping Europe's research future. This commitment will not only strengthen Ireland's influence within the EU but also affirm its role in advancing a cohesive and innovative European research infrastructure.

As a first step in developing EOSC Ireland it is recommended that a Coordination and Support Action be established. The proposed Coordination & Support Action (CSA) will:

- Define detailed use cases and scaling strategies for EOSC Ireland.
- Specify organisational cost structures for participation in the EOSC Ireland node.
- Outline the operational model for implementing a federated EOSC approach in the Irish context.
- Recommend solutions to ensure accessibility, security, and regulatory compliance.
- Facilitate cross-departmental alignment to advance digital integration between research and enterprise through Open Science.
- Provide strategic input to the IMPACT2030 Committee ahead of Ireland's EU Presidency and contribute to the NORF National Action Plan Review.

Key Recommendations

- **Designate a Coordinating Organisation:** Assign an entity to lead the Coordination and Support Action (CSA).
- **Develop Project Charter and Terms of Reference:** Specify the charter and ToR to guide Work Packages operations and ensure effective delivery.
- **Allocate Financial Resources:** Provide funding for personnel, logistics, and pilot activities, including Proofs of Concept.
- **Endorse WP Outcomes:** Officially recognise WP outputs to ensure their integration into the establishment of the ongoing EOSC Ireland initiative.

The success of EOSC Ireland depends on a well-funded, approved implementation plan that aligns with national and European priorities. By embedding within the broader EOSC ecosystem, Ireland can strengthen its research infrastructure and advance its Open Research goals. The commitment of key organisations (HEAnet, ICHEC, RPOs) fortifies the plan's viability and paves the way for impactful execution.

⁴ [National Action Plan for Open Research](#)

⁵ [Open Data Strategy 2023-2027](#)

To successfully implement EOSC Ireland, an initial investment of approximately **€578,000** is required for the one-year Coordination and Support Action (CSA), as detailed in Appendix 1. This figure is consistent with the funding levels allocated to EOSC nodes in other European countries, as evidenced in Appendix 2.

This initial allocation represents only the foundational phase of EOSC Ireland. To ensure full implementation, integration into the EOSC federation, and sustained operational capacity, additional strategic investments will be essential. The projected total cost over a five-year period is estimated to be in the range of €9–10 million.

The CSA will be responsible for defining the funding and business model necessary to support these costs, ensuring long-term viability and alignment with European Open Science Cloud objectives.

1. Introduction

This position paper proposes the development of a national EOSC Node for Ireland - **EOSC Ireland** - modelled on the technical infrastructure of the EOSC EU Node. It outlines the strategic importance of establishing EOSC Ireland as a key enabler of national and international research collaboration, improved access to digital research infrastructures, and alignment with European Open Research policies.

Beyond technical implementation, this paper highlights the broader value of EOSC Ireland in fostering interoperability across research domains, lowering barriers to data access, and supporting the secure, standards-based exchange of services and knowledge. It identifies the actions, requirements, and gaps necessary to ensure Ireland's successful integration into the EOSC Federation, and positions EOSC Ireland as a foundational step toward a more connected, competitive, and impactful national research ecosystem.

1.1 What is EOSC?

The **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**⁶ is a long-term initiative by the European Commission to create a unified environment for managing and sharing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and services across all scientific disciplines. Central to this vision is the EOSC Federation, a network of interconnected national, regional, institutional, and thematic research infrastructures. Through this federated model, EOSC enables seamless collaboration and access to research resources across Europe, fostering Open Research and enhancing the impact of data-driven research. Fundamentally, EOSC aims to accelerate reproducible scientific discovery and innovation (EOSC, 2023)⁷.

In this context, **Research Infrastructure** refers to the foundational systems, services, and resources -

⁶ [Building the EOSC Federation](#)

⁷ [EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap \(MAR\)](#)

both technical and organisational - that support the creation, sharing, analysis, preservation, and governance of research data and digital scholarship. Technical infrastructure incorporates the hardware, software, networks, and platforms (e.g. data repositories, compute clusters, authentication systems) that enable data storage, processing, and access. Social infrastructure refers to the human and institutional frameworks - such as policies, governance structures, training programs, and communities of practice - that ensure the effective and ethical use of technical systems and foster collaboration and trust among stakeholders.

While the EOSC Ireland Node represents a significant technical infrastructure development, its success is also dependent on robust social and organisational frameworks that enable sustained collaboration and governance. EOSC is fundamentally built on the integration of both technical and organisational layers of European IT and research service infrastructures, reflecting a comprehensive approach to enabling Open Research at scale.

*The **EOSC Federation** aims to provide Europe's researchers with the necessary digital resources to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders according to the principles of FAIR data and open science, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.*

This will be done by putting in place a so-called 'system of systems' with an appropriate organisational and operational structure, between institutional, regional, national, and European data repositories, research infrastructures, e-infrastructure and other scientific service providers federated into a network of nodes — the EOSC Nodes.

*An **EOSC Node** will be typically formed by multiple research institutes, universities and other stakeholders with a common geographical (European, regional or national) or thematic scope.*

The expected outcomes of the EOSC Federation are as follows:

- *Enhanced access to and use of digital resources*
- *Facilitated research reproducibility*
- *Increased collaboration, community and knowledge sharing*
- *Improved efficiency and higher impact of investment in research*
- *Increased standardisation and interoperability*
- *Better support for thematic initiatives*
- *Improved research integrity*
- *Increased robustness and trustworthiness*
- *Increased data sovereignty*

(EOSC, 2025)⁸

⁸ [EOSC Federation Handbook](#)

Open Science is defined by UNESCO as “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community” (UNESCO, 2021)⁹.

1.2 National Commitment to EOSC

HEAnet, Ireland’s National Education and Research Network (NREN), is formally mandated by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS) as the national organisation responsible for coordinating Ireland’s engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In April 2024, HEAnet’s Research Engagement Team published *A Vision to Implement the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland*¹⁰, setting out a strategic action plan to advance Ireland’s research ecosystem through active participation in EOSC.

Since then, this vision has evolved into a national initiative, shaped through collaboration with key stakeholders across the Irish research and innovation landscape. Contributors include University College Dublin (UCD), University College Cork (UCC), Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI), Dublin City University (DCU), University of Limerick (UL), the National Open Research Forum (NORF), Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin), the Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC), the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI), Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Technological University of the Shannon (TUS), Atlantic Technological University (ATU), South East Technological University (SETU), University of Galway, National Disability Authority, Health Research Board (HRB) and Research Ireland. Their collective engagement reflects a shared commitment to building a coordinated, inclusive, and future-ready EOSC Ireland.

Ireland has committed to Action 1 of the European Research Area (ERA) priorities - Open Science. EOSC Ireland delivers on this commitment. This national effort aligns with significant developments at the European level. In 2024, the European Commission launched the EOSC EU Node¹¹; the first operational node in the EOSC Federation. This technical infrastructure serves as a pilot gateway for researchers, offering access to advanced services such as bulk data transfer, large file exchange, virtual machines, cloud container platforms, interactive notebooks, and file ‘sync and share’. As a reference model for future nodes, it underscores the importance of integrating national efforts like EOSC Ireland into the broader EOSC Federation, to ensure interoperability, scalability, and impact.

⁹ [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#)

¹⁰ [A Vision to Implement the European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) in Ireland](#)

¹¹ [EOSC EU Node](#)

1.3 Broader Impact on Ireland's Research & Development Eco-System

By fostering a collaborative, secure, efficient, and trustworthy research environment, EOSC drives economic growth and innovation while advancing the Open Research movement¹². It empowers researchers to share and reuse data across disciplines and borders, reduces duplication of effort, and ensures compliance with FAIR and open science principles. In doing so, EOSC provides a common infrastructure for funded research, and supports innovation and evidence-based policymaking. For Ireland, active participation in EOSC represents a strategic investment in the future of research, education, and digital infrastructure. These themes are further elucidated in Section 7 Motivation & Opportunities.

¹² [Why EOSC is Pivotal to European Competitiveness.](#)

2. Vision

This paper proposes the establishment of EOSC Ireland, a national node within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation.

2.1 Overarching Vision

The EOSC Federation is being developed as a network of interoperable nodes that are interconnected and can collaborate across thematic and geographical research communities. EOSC Nodes will serve as entry points for users to a broad range of services, and with each node offering its own and third-party services, including repositories, compute or software.

EOSC Ireland will function as a technical infrastructure, built on software middleware that connects Ireland's research services and infrastructures to the wider EOSC ecosystem. It will act as a digital platform that enables seamless integration between institutional systems and European services.

Through EOSC Ireland, higher education institutions will be able to provide researchers and students with streamlined access to high-quality, FAIR-aligned data and tools. This access will be delivered through familiar institutional research IT environments, while also extending to trusted third-party services across the EU.

The node will support both data sharing and controlled access, with resource providers retaining authority over how their services are used. This ensures flexibility and compliance with national and institutional policies.

Unlike commercial platforms, EOSC Ireland will operate under principles of European digital sovereignty. It will be shaped by the coordinated effort of the research and innovation stakeholder community and established infrastructures, ensuring openness, interoperability, and long-term sustainability.

EOSC Ireland must be designed to cater to all levels of research, including small-scale use cases, while enabling scalability and efficiency. Through EOSC Ireland, researchers will be able to discover and contribute datasets, share analytical tools and workflows, and collaborate more easily across disciplines and borders. Further, by training researchers on EOSC Ireland, they will be equipped to engage with European research infrastructures and standards, while also being future-proofed for careers in data-intensive industries, including AI and digital health.

EOSC Ireland will build on synergies with key national initiatives - including Impact 2030, NORF, IRL-DataSpace, and the national HPC and data platform - to advance data sharing, interoperability, and support for complex research workflows. Through strategic integration with these efforts, EOSC Ireland will drive innovation, foster collaboration, and accelerate scientific discovery, ensuring that Ireland's research community remains globally competitive and at the cutting edge of research excellence.

2.2 Practical View

EOSC Ireland will serve as a *single point of access* to a wide range of research services and resources, operating within a federated '**system of systems**.' This approach ensures that diverse infrastructures - national, institutional, and domain-specific - can be connected and accessed through a unified platform.

The node will enable integration with key national Tier-1 infrastructures, such as those provided by the Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC), as well as with specialised platforms such as the Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA) and ELIXIR Ireland. It will be especially useful in linking diverse school/college level and multi-institution domain-specific resources to provide an EU-integrated/supported platform for efficient management of authentication and access (e.g. iCIRAG geoscience).

EOSC Ireland will support the cataloguing, discovery and use of:

- Data sets
- Data services
- Data workflows and open-source software
- High performance computing (HPC) and data processing services
- Storage services
- Virtual Research Environments (VRE)
- Applications

Fig 1: Illustrative example of EOSC Ireland; its core functions, together with services and resources provided by third-party organisations

EOSC Ireland will help enable the high-quality, well-governed and interoperable data essential for training and deploying AI systems, which depends on secure, large-scale access to diverse health and research datasets to drive innovation in patient care and clinical decision-making.

Appendix 3 includes an initial overview of national, institutional and thematic infrastructures and services they would be suitable for onboarding to EOSC Ireland, with this list assumed to evolve and development over time.; it is a 'place in time' assessment.

2.2.1 Leadership

Given the ongoing collaborative work between ICHEC and HEAnet on the IRL-Dataspace initiative - and the natural complementarity of this work with the development of EOSC Ireland - it is currently envisaged that both organisations would play a strategic role in the implementation and operation of the EOSC Ireland node.

As national providers of digital infrastructure, ICHEC and HEAnet bring valuable experience and capabilities that could support the delivery of a robust and effective EOSC Ireland. Their continued collaboration would build on existing synergies, helping to ensure that the node is well-aligned with national priorities while also contributing to the broader European Open Research ecosystem.

This approach presents a strong opportunity to leverage existing momentum and partnerships in a way that benefits the research community and supports Ireland's evolving digital research infrastructure.

2.3 EOSC Ireland Features & Benefits

1. Comprehensive Monitoring and Accounting Services

- EOSC Ireland will implement robust systems to monitor and account for resource usage, allowing researchers to pay for what they use through flexible mechanisms such as credits-based systems or digital wallets.
- This ensures transparency and fairness in resource allocation, while also enabling institutions and funders to track expenditures and usage patterns effectively.

2. Integration with the EOSC Federation

- EOSC Ireland will connect seamlessly with the Europe-wide EOSC Federation, expanding the reach of Irish research services beyond national borders.
- Researchers will benefit from the ability to combine local resources with international ones, fostering cross-border collaboration and enhancing the competitiveness of Irish research on the global stage.

3. Closing Gaps in National Infrastructure

EOSC Ireland will address critical gaps by establishing foundational services such as:

- A national resource catalogue and registry
- Identity and access management systems
- Service monitoring and performance tracking

4. Policy-Aligned Resource Access

- Access to research infrastructures will be governed by institutional and funder policies, ensuring compliance and strategic alignment.
- This structure allows research services to be marketed to relevant institutional and external communities, supporting broader engagement while managing both operational and capital expenditures efficiently.

5. **Secure Handling of Sensitive Data**

- Services designed for sensitive data will be accessible via EOSC Ireland, supporting compliance with legal and ethical requirements.
- EOSC Ireland will enable federated data processing, where algorithms and computing resources are brought to the data, rather than moving data across jurisdictions – ‘data visitation’ - ensuring privacy, reducing costs, and improving efficiency in handling large or sensitive datasets.

6. **Onboarding of Diverse Research Resources**

- The platform will integrate national HPC and data storage facilities, institutional compute and storage services, and thematic research infrastructures.
- This aggregation will form a **Minimum Viable Product (MVP)** that is immediately useful to researchers, offering a unified and accessible environment for data-intensive research. The MVP is the starting position of EOSC Ireland, which will necessarily evolve over time.

7. **Platform for Innovation in Open Research**

- EOSC Ireland will serve as a launchpad for innovative services and solutions emerging from research initiatives and future EOSC-funded calls under FP10.
- It will support experimentation, prototyping, reproducibility and scaling of new tools and methodologies that advance the principles of Open Research.

8. **Marketplace for Research Infrastructure and Upskilling**

- The node will act as a dynamic marketplace, promoting the exchange of research infrastructure and training opportunities.
- It will enhance national capacity in research data management by familiarising communities with best practices and tools, and by offering targeted upskilling initiatives.
- This will catalyse the development of underlying data infrastructures and drive technical automation, ultimately improving the efficiency and impact of Irish research.

3. Requirements for the EOSC Ireland node

There are 3 required phases for the implementation of EOSC Ireland:

1. Developing and enabling core functions
2. Onboarding resources and services to have a **Minimum Viable Product (MVP)** useful to researchers
3. Connecting EOSC Ireland to the EOSC Federation

EOSC Ireland over time will continuously evolve beyond its starting point (MVP), outlined below. Over time, additional services will be integrated into the EOSC Ireland node as providers become ready to onboard. These may include both existing services and new, innovative offerings emerging from ongoing research and development. Successfully expanding the node will depend on close collaboration between EOSC Ireland, innovators, and emerging service providers, ensuring that new capabilities are aligned with community needs and technical standards.

3.1 Core Functions

3.1.1 Requirements

The Core Functions are described in detail in the EOSC Federation Handbook¹³ and comprise:

- Resource catalogue and registry services
- Identity management, providing single sign-on to the resources and services connected.
- Service monitoring and accounting
- Order management, where users can request services and pay for them where applicable
- Helpdesk and service management
- Application workflow management, for example to enable researchers to deploy applications on compute resources, download data from connected repositories onto storage resources

These functions require the availability of an organisation providing the helpdesk and service management functions, and owning the implementation of all the other components, although third parties may provide the functions such as order management and workflow management and IT infrastructure to run the above functions.

These core operational functions, combined with the other services and activities previously described, will ensure Ireland will have a fully functional infrastructure to enable Open Research in Ireland.

¹³ [EOSC Federation Handbook](#).

Fig 2: Illustrative example of EOSC Ireland core operational functions

In terms of skills required to perform the core functions, these are noted:

- System administration
- Platform engineering
- Data management
- Cybersecurity
- Legal/Data protection
- Governance

3.1.2 Readiness

Of the core functions, Ireland currently only avails of the Identity Management system, which is based on HEAnet's Edugate¹⁴ federated single sign on (SSO) service.

An Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) compatible with the *EOSC AAI Architecture 2025*¹⁵ is currently not available. This would have to be implemented and would be based on GÉANT¹⁶'s MyAccessID¹⁷ Identity and Access Management Service.

¹⁴ [Edugate](#)

¹⁵ [EOSC AAI Architecture 2025](#)

¹⁶ [GÉANT](#) is the collaboration of European National Research and Education Networks (NRENs)

¹⁷ [MyAccessID](#)

The core node functions such as the registry of services, accounting and monitoring, and workflow management are not generally available. Whilst the EOSC EU node makes these functions available as open source, there is no support offered in their usage.

Additionally, Ireland does not, at present, have an organisation assigned to operating the core node functions, or allocated infrastructure on which to run these.

These gaps can be addressed by leveraging solutions deployed in other countries, such as [Research Cloud software](#) developed by SURF. Research Cloud is also being considered for use by Sunet¹⁸ in Sweden and Switch¹⁹ in Switzerland for the same purpose.

3.2 Onboarding Resources and Services

3.2.1 Requirements

The core functionality outlined above is foundational but not sufficient to constitute an MVP, as no services or resources are yet connected to the EOSC Ireland node. To make the platform genuinely useful to researchers, relevant services must be onboarded and integrated into a shared resource catalogue. This onboarding process is essential to transforming the node from a technical framework into a functional, researcher-facing environment.

Relevant services could be a combination of any of the following:

- National HPC and data storage resources and services
- Institutional compute and storage services
- Research data repositories (thematic or institutional)
- Thematic Research Infrastructures (such as those described above)

¹⁸ [Sunet](#) is the National Research and Education Network (NREN) in Sweden

¹⁹ [Switch](#) is the National Research and Education Network (NREN) in Switzerland

Fig 3: Illustrative example of an EOSC Ireland MVP

3.2.2 Readiness

Several services are currently planned in Ireland which could be connected to an EOSC Ireland node, depending on readiness:

National HPC and Data Platform

The national high-performance computing (HPC) and data platform is currently under review by DFHERIS for a potential upgrade. The production IRLDAT platform is expected to become available in 2025, significantly strengthening Ireland's national research infrastructure.

Institutional Resources

Several institutional resources are already established, including RCSI's infrastructure, UCD's next-generation Sonic HPC, and Dropbox's active store and share services. However, onboarding these into the EOSC Ireland node will require formal institutional approvals, along with the development of governance structures, security protocols, and sustainable funding and budgeting models

Thematic and Institutional Repositories and Infrastructures

A number of thematic and institutional repositories and infrastructures are available, such as the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI). Infrastructures under development, with planned availability in 2025, include, GDI-Ireland, UCD's SES Caldera, and new infrastructure at DCU. Once operational, they will provide valuable domain-specific capabilities to the EOSC Ireland ecosystem.

Research Infrastructure (RI) Centre-Based Resources

Research infrastructure (RI) centre-based resources such as the iCrag geodata repository will play a key role in enriching the EOSC Ireland node. These specialised infrastructures will support advanced research in targeted disciplines and contribute to a more diverse and comprehensive national research platform.

Successfully onboarding these resources into the EOSC Ireland core service will require the development of robust registry and Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) systems. These are not optional enhancements but essential components that must be clearly defined, resourced, and implemented. Establishing these requirements is a key recommendation of this document and will be informed by the practical insights gained from the development of the EOSC Federation. This work is critical to ensuring that EOSC Ireland is not only operational but also scalable, secure, and aligned with European best practices.

3.3 Enrolling EOSC Ireland as part of the EOSC Federation

3.3.1 Requirements

Once operational, the EOSC Ireland node has the potential to become a formal part of the broader EOSC Federation, thereby extending its scope from a national infrastructure to a contributor within a pan-European - and ultimately global - Open Research ecosystem. This integration is a critical step in ensuring that Irish research infrastructures are interoperable with European counterparts and aligned with international standards for data sharing, access, and governance.

Currently, there are two recognised modalities for joining the EOSC Federation:

1. Onboarding a Service to an Existing EOSC Node

This approach allows individual services to be integrated into an already established EOSC node. For example, CERN has adopted this model for onboarding Zenodo, enabling them to gain experience and visibility within the EOSC ecosystem without building a full node from the outset.

2. Enrolment of a New EOSC Node

This involves the development of a dedicated EOSC node and its formal inclusion in the Federation, following the technical and governance guidelines outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook. New contributions to the Federation are now expected to follow this model, as it provides a more comprehensive and sustainable integration pathway.

Ireland must federate its resources regardless, and doing so through a dedicated EOSC Ireland node is both more strategic and advantageous. It ensures national services are developed under Irish governance while aligning with European frameworks, enabling Ireland to contribute more effectively to the future of Open Research in Europe.

Enrolling an EOSC-node into the EOSC federation requires the following:

- Compliance with the EOSC federation AAI²⁰
- The organisation ('EOSC Node Host') running EOSC Ireland must be a legal entity.

²⁰ [EOSC AAI Architecture 2025](#)

- The organisation must have a Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) function and conduct Cybersecurity management according to established best practices and applicable standards.
- The EOSC Ireland Registry of Resources must be pushed to the EOSC Federation registry so researchers from other countries can find and access resources from Ireland. Access must be managed, and resources must be monitored and the node continuously developed.
- Sustainable funding for the infrastructure, its management, and the organisation responsible for it.

Further, to facilitate the interaction of the Node with the Federation, each Node must nominate persons in the following roles²¹:

1. A **Coordinator** who represents the Node in the Federation.
2. An **Operation Manager** who is the contact person with the Operations Team of the Federation on operations.
3. A **Technical Coordinator** who is the contact person with the Technical Coordination Team of the Federation on technical issues (mainly IT issues).
4. A **Security Officer** who is the contact person for all security related issues.
5. A **Legal/Privacy Officer** for legal issues.

3.3.2 Readiness

As outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook, each EOSC Node must be represented at the Federation level by a legal organisation or entity. This representative body may be an existing legal entity already embedded within the national research infrastructure, or it may be necessary to establish a new entity specifically for this purpose. Determining the most appropriate legal structure for EOSC Ireland will be a critical step in ensuring compliance with Federation requirements and enabling effective participation at the European level.

In addition to legal representation, the EOSC Federation requires that each node has access to a Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) function. This ensures that nodes can respond appropriately to security incidents and maintain the integrity of the federated environment. This requirement is already well supported within the Irish research landscape, where CSIRT capabilities are mature and operational across key institutions.

Another essential requirement for federation is the ability to push the EOSC Ireland Registry of Resources to the EOSC Federation Registry. The requirements and technical specifications for registry integration within the EOSC federation are currently being developed by the EOSC Federation build up group.

To address these foundational requirements and ensure a coordinated national approach, this document recommends the establishment of dedicated work packages focused on national

²¹ [EOSC Federation Handbook](#)

governance. These work packages will be tasked with defining the legal, technical, and procedural frameworks necessary for EOSC Ireland's successful enrolment into the EOSC Federation.

4. National Readiness for EOSC Ireland

Since 2018, a range of national and European initiatives involving Irish organisations have demonstrated the knowledge, infrastructure, and commitment necessary to advance a national EOSC Node. These efforts reflect Ireland’s growing capacity to contribute meaningfully to the EOSC Federation.

Overseen by NORF, the National Action Plan for Open Research provides a coordinated framework for advancing Open Research in Ireland. The broader Open Research context, including infrastructure and policy, is detailed in Appendix 4.

The 2021 *National Open Research Landscape Report*²² identified five defining areas of infrastructure support:

1. **Networking and Computing Infrastructures**
 - Computing and storage infrastructure
 - Identity and access management
2. **Meta-Infrastructures**
 - Persistent identifiers and related services
3. **Data Infrastructures**
 - Data processing and secure research environments
 - Institutional and national research data repositories
 - Publication platforms and metadata aggregation services
4. **Thematic/Disciplinary Infrastructures**
5. **Quality Criteria**
 - Repository certification and standards for data quality and governance

Fig 4: Irish Research Landscape

²² [National Open Research Landscape Report](#).

4.1 National and European Engagements

1. **EOSC FAIR-Impact Project**
 - DRI and HEAnet have developed a national framework for FAIR-aligned solutions.
 - A national Persistent Identifier (PID) roadmap has been established as a key component of this work.
2. **EOSC PORTAL & EU Node Participation**
 - DRI contributed to the original EOSC pilot portal (eosc-portal.eu), now succeeded by the EOSC EU Node launched in 2024.
3. **OCRE Procurement Frameworks**
 - HEAnet has led Ireland's participation in successive OCRE frameworks with GÉANT which have been leveraged to implemented to integrate commercial digital services into EOSC.
4. **EOSC-Future Project and Cascade Funding**
 - Defined technical and contractual models for node implementation.
 - Two Irish R&D projects received cascade funding:
 - **QCloud (MTU)**: Aggregated cloud-based access to quantum computing hardware.
 - **iCRAG/UCD**: Open access to commercial geosurvey data for use by iCRAG and TCD researchers.
5. **IRLDAT Shared Storage Service**
 - Developed by HEAnet, ICHEC and Irish HEI IT Services in collaboration with EUDAT, supporting FAIR principles and the full research data lifecycle.

4.2 National Social & Organisational Infrastructure

Ireland's readiness to establish an EOSC Node is underpinned not only by technical capacity but also by a strong and evolving social and organisational infrastructure. This includes well-established communities of practice, national coordination mechanisms, and cross-institutional collaboration frameworks that are essential for the sustainable implementation of EOSC Ireland.

National Open Research Forum (NORF)

NORF plays a central role in coordinating Ireland's Open Research agenda. Through its funding and policy initiatives, NORF has fostered strong community engagement across higher education institutions, libraries, research offices, and IT services. These efforts have built a shared understanding of Open Research principles and laid the groundwork for collaborative governance models. NORF has supported a range of training programmes, workshops, and community-building activities that have increased awareness and readiness for Open Science practices. These initiatives have helped embed a culture of collaboration, transparency, and data sharing across disciplines and institutions.

Sonraí: National Data Stewardship Network

Sonraí is a national initiative focused on building capacity in data stewardship across Irish research institutions. It supports the development of professional roles, training, and best practices for managing FAIR data, ensuring that Ireland has the human infrastructure needed to support EOSC-aligned data governance and quality standards.

Research Support and Engagement Infrastructure Network (RESIN)

The RESIN group brings together research support professionals from across Irish HEIs to share expertise, align institutional practices, and coordinate responses to national and European research infrastructure developments. RESIN plays a key role in bridging administrative and academic functions, ensuring that EOSC implementation is embedded in institutional workflow.

4.3 National High-Performance Computing & Data Platform

The development of Ireland's next-generation national High-Performance Computing (HPC) and data platform, to be delivered by the Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC), is currently under review by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS). This platform is envisioned as a critical component of Ireland's digital research infrastructure, designed to support a wide range of national and European research and innovation priorities.

The platform will comprise advanced high-performance computing capabilities and large-scale data storage infrastructure. It will serve as the Tier-1 national facility, providing the digital backbone for research and innovation across disciplines. In addition to supporting national needs, it will federate with Tier-2 infrastructures - such as thematic and institutional compute and data services - and integrate with European-level resources, including European HPC and EOSC-aligned infrastructures.

To ensure secure, efficient, and compliant access to these resources, the platform will incorporate robust access gateways. These will facilitate high-performance data exchange while upholding stringent standards for data governance, privacy, and security. This is particularly important for enabling the integration and analysis of diverse datasets required to address complex, cross-sectoral challenges.

In this context, the national HPC and data platform is well-positioned to serve as the foundational infrastructure for the sustainable development and operation of EOSC Nodes in Ireland. This includes the proposed EOSC Ireland Node, which would benefit from the platform's scalability, performance, and alignment with European digital research infrastructure standards

An illustrative case study is presented in Appendix 5.

4.4 Research Cloud: Leveraging European Expertise and Collaboration

Should Ireland be in a position to make a timely decision on the Coordination and Support Action

(CSA), there is a unique and time-sensitive opportunity to leverage proven European infrastructure to accelerate the development of EOSC Ireland. SURF, the Dutch national research and education network, has successfully implemented **ResearchCloud**—a secure, cloud-based portal that provides Dutch researchers and their collaborators with seamless access to data, compute resources, and services. This model closely mirrors the architecture and service delivery approach of the EOSC EU Node.

Recognising this alignment, SURF has announced plans to base their national EOSC Node on the ResearchCloud platform. With their support, Ireland has the opportunity to conduct a Proof of Concept (PoC) trial using ResearchCloud to explore how it could serve as the foundation for the EOSC Ireland Node.

This collaboration offers a secure, cost-effective, and low-risk pathway to test and validate EOSC Node implementation in an Irish context. It builds on Ireland's successful engagement with EOSC to date and provides a practical mechanism to accelerate progress while aligning with European best practices. However, this opportunity is time-sensitive and contingent on Ireland's ability to act decisively within the current CSA planning window.

Examples of EOSC node provision in other countries appear in Appendix 6.

5. SWOT Analysis

5.1 Strengths

- **Established National Expertise:** Ireland already has strong digital infrastructure providers (e.g. HEAnet, ICHEC), including mature CSIRT capabilities, which can support secure and reliable EOSC node operations. Ongoing collaboration between HEAnet and ICHEC on IRL-Dataspace provides a strong operational and technical foundation for EOSC Ireland.
- **Existing Investment in Research Infrastructure**
Ireland has already made investments in digital research infrastructure. EOSC Ireland offers a coordinated platform to maximise the return on this investment and avoid duplication.
- **Alignment with EU Sovereignty and FAIR Principles**
EOSC Ireland supports a sovereign, EU-based infrastructure aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, reducing reliance on non-EU commercial providers and reinforcing digital autonomy.
- **Social Infrastructure for Research Collaboration**
Ireland's strong social infrastructure - built through national forums like NORF and long-standing inter-institutional collaboration - supports coordinated action, shared governance, and community engagement. This collaborative environment is a key enabler for the successful rollout and sustainability of EOSC Ireland.

5.2 Weaknesses

- **Lack of Legal Entity:** EOSC Ireland currently lacks a designated legal entity to represent it at the Federation level, which is a critical requirement for enrolment.
- **Lack of a Coordinated National Node**
Without a dedicated EOSC Ireland node, national research infrastructures risk continuing in a fragmented and siloed manner, leading to inefficiencies and higher operational costs.
- **Limited Current Engagement**
While there has been some local engagement with EOSC EU nodes, it has not been coordinated or strategic. This limits Ireland's influence and visibility within the broader EOSC ecosystem.
- **Registry Integration:** The ability to push the EOSC Ireland Registry to the Federation Registry is not yet implemented, requiring additional development and coordination.
- **Governance Gaps:** National governance structures, procedures, and funding models for EOSC Ireland are not yet defined, posing a risk to timely implementation.

5.3 Opportunities

- **Enhanced International Reputation and Influence**
Participation in the EOSC Federation would reinforce Ireland's position as a leader in Open Research and research innovation, supporting national goals such as those outlined in *Impact 2030*.

- **Improved Research Efficiency and Economic Integration**
EOSC promotes standardisation, interoperability, and commercial engagement. Ireland's participation would increase the efficiency of research investments and open new pathways for innovation and commercialisation.
- **Capacity Building:** The process of establishing governance, legal structures, and technical systems will strengthen Ireland's national research infrastructure and policy coherence. EOSC Ireland would provide a platform for digital upskilling of researchers, with skills and tools that are transferable across the EU, strengthening Ireland's research capacity and talent pipeline.
- **Access to FP10 and Strategic Research Domains**
An EOSC Ireland node would enable Irish researchers to fully participate in Horizon Europe FP10 projects, particularly in high-priority areas like Industry 4.0, AI, and Climate Resilience, which require access to federated, high-capacity digital infrastructure.
- **Innovation and Interoperability:** EOSC Ireland can serve as a platform for onboarding innovative services and fostering interoperability across national and European research services.
- **Leverage Existing Tools:** Adoption of proven tools like SURF's Research Cloud can accelerate technical readiness and reduce development overhead.
- **EU Health Data Space (EHDS)**
EOSC is positioned as a core infrastructure for enabling secondary use of health data under the EHDS. EOSC Ireland would ensure national readiness to meet these statutory obligations.

5.4 Threats

- **Reputational Risk from Non-Participation**
Failure to engage with the EOSC Federation could damage Ireland's reputation in the international research community, undermining its ability to attract top-tier talent and investment.
- **Reduced Return on Investment**
Without integration into EOSC, Ireland risks lower returns on its existing research infrastructure investments due to lack of coordination, duplication of effort, and missed opportunities for shared services.
- **Strategic Isolation**
As the EOSC Federation moves toward national node enrolment (Wave 2), countries without a node may find themselves increasingly isolated from EU research infrastructure planning and funding mechanisms.
- **Delays in Legal and Governance Setup:** Prolonged uncertainty around the legal entity and governance model could delay enrolment and reduce Ireland's competitiveness in EOSC.
- **Funding Uncertainty:** Implementation depends on sustained funding and institutional commitment, which may be subject to delays or shifting priorities.

- **Loss of Momentum:** Without coordinated national leadership and clear timelines, there is a risk of losing the current momentum and stakeholder engagement.

The European Union Presidency

Ireland's upcoming EU Presidency from July to December 2026 marks a pivotal moment to assert leadership in shaping Europe's research and innovation landscape. Active engagement with the EOSC Federation during this period is not only timely—it is essential. It will signal Ireland's strategic commitment to advancing European research infrastructure, data governance, and Open Science policy. By contributing meaningfully to the EOSC Federation, Ireland can elevate its influence within EU decision-making circles, reinforce its reputation as a research leader, and ensure that national priorities are reflected in the future direction of European science and innovation.

6. Recommended Actions

Considering the national vision for EOSC Ireland, the current gaps in Ireland's research infrastructure, and the clear synergies with other national initiatives, a strategic and coordinated approach is essential to move from planning to implementation. To support this transition, it is recommended that a **Coordination and Support Action (CSA)** be established as a preparatory phase. This CSA will provide the necessary structure, stakeholder engagement, and technical groundwork to enable EOSC Ireland to progress toward full operationalisation in the next phase of development.

Across 12 months and 7 work packages, the CSA will:

- Make recommendations for EOSC Ireland governance
- Articulate how the EOSC-based federated approach will work for Ireland
- Scope and plan out detailed use cases and scaling
- Describe and recommend solutions for ease of access, security and compliance
- Determine organisational costs for EOSC Ireland node establishment and development
- Support building cross-departmental consensus to address Irish research-enterprise digital integration through Open Research
- Provide input to the IMPACT2030 committee in time for the Irish EU presidency, and contribute to the NORF National Action Plan Review

It is essential that DFHERIS supports this by:

1. **Appointing a Coordinating Organisation**

Designate an organisation to oversee the CSA leading to the implementation of EOSC Ireland. This organisation will be responsible for coordinating activities, managing finances and budgets, and ensuring alignment with the CSA objectives.

2. **Setting Out Project Charter and Terms of Reference (ToR)**

Assist in defining the overall Project Charter and the Terms of Reference for the WPs. Formally approve these documents to support the project's activities and objectives effectively.

3. **Providing Financial Support**

Allocate funds for project staff time, meeting facilities, and associated ancillary costs. This financial support will enable the WPs to conduct their work, perform trials, and execute Proofs of Concepts (PoC) for EOSC node development funding mechanisms and relevant technologies.

4. **Recognising WP Results**

Acknowledge the results produced by the WPs as authoritative. This recognition will ensure that the findings and recommendations of the WPs are implemented and integrated into the EOSC Ireland project.

5. **Recognising this project as a cross-departmental initiative on RI&I and Upskilling**

Avoiding siloes by agreeing an approach to engagement with DETI, DPENDR and those with thematic interests and responsibilities (e.g. Health, DCEE), plus their aegis bodies such as Enterprise Ireland.

6.1 Recommended Work Packages

WORK PACKAGES
WP0: PROJECT MANAGEMENT & COORDINATION (LEAD: HEANET)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Management, Coordination, Oversight and Reporting, Budget Management
WP1: TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE (LEAD: ICHEC)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical architecture, including analysis of synergies with other national initiatives to leverage them for a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for EOSC Ireland Develop a technical roadmap for EOSC Ireland, highlighting how it will support continuous evolution and innovation and steps to be taken to connect research data repositories
WP2: TECHNICAL TRIALS (LEAD: ICHEC)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct technical trials/PoCs of relevant technologies, such as Research Cloud and any other deemed relevant, including integrations of external (national and institutional) services with the node
WP3: DEFINING THE ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE (LEAD: TU DUBLIN)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Determine the organisational structure for the day-to-day operations of EOSC Ireland and its governance in the longer term In collaboration with WP1, it will set out the types of roles that are required to develop and operate the EOSC Ireland node Establish a sustainable funding model with associated legal and organisational relationships, and required costings Consider whether a new legal entity needs to be established. Establish and test relevant legal and organisational relationships as part of the CSA
WP4: TECHNICAL PLANNING FOR CONNECTING TO THE EOSC FEDERATION (LEAD: UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical planning for joining the EOSC Federation
WP5: TECHNICAL PLANNING FOR SERVICES FOR HANDLING SENSITIVE DATA (LEAD: TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical planning for connecting to services for handling sensitive data This will concern primarily certifications, compliances needed by an EOSC Ireland node to connect to such services hence enabling access to them from users who connect via the EOSC Ireland node
WP6: COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT, DISSEMINATION AND TRAINING (LEAD: HEANET)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued community communication and engagement Development of training materials, e.g. liaise with Skillsnet regarding industry skills Run community stakeholder engagement events

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce materials for dissemination • Set up and manage stakeholder advisory fora |
|--|

Table 1: Proposed Work Packages for CSA

It is anticipated that the CSA will culminate in the development of a comprehensive implementation plan, which will be submitted for approval and funding. Upon approval, this plan will guide the next phase of activity, including the rollout of technical infrastructure, stakeholder engagement and communication, training and capacity building, monitoring and evaluation, sustainability planning, and integration with broader national and European initiatives.

A detailed project plan and budget for the CSA is provided in Appendix 1. Notably, several organisations have already expressed interest in leading or contributing to the proposed work packages, underscoring both the viability of the action plan and the strong national commitment to the success of EOSC Ireland.

6.2 Continued Support for Open Research in Ireland

It is further recommended that support for Open Research in Ireland is maintained by:

- **Implement the National Persistent Identifier (PID) Roadmap and Strategy**
Prioritise the execution of the national PID roadmap to ensure consistent, interoperable identification of research outputs, infrastructure, and contributors across the research ecosystem.
- **Continued Funding for NORF and the National Action Plan for Open Research (2022–2030)**
Maintain and, where possible, expand financial support for NORF and the implementation of the National Action Plan. Consider the development of long-term, sustainable funding models to secure their impact and continuity.
- **Ensure Sustainable Investment in Critical Research Infrastructures**
Provide stable funding for essential infrastructures such as National High-Performance Computing (HPC), platforms supporting secondary use of health data under the EHDS (e.g. ELIXIR), and services for managing sensitive research data.
- **Support the Establishment of a National Open-Source Program Office (OSPO)**
Facilitate the creation of a national OSPO to promote the adoption, development, and governance of open-source software in research and innovation.
- **Advance Repository Standards and Alignment**
Invest in the development of repository standards and best practices, building on the work of the Open Repositories Ireland (ORI) project. This is essential for enabling Irish data repositories to connect effectively with EOSC Ireland and meet European interoperability requirements.
- **Define and Coordinate Areas of Responsibility**
Develop and communicate clearly defined roles and responsibilities across DFHERIS, aegis bodies, funding agencies, and institutions. This coordination is vital to ensure the sustainability of research data infrastructure and to maximise its economic and societal benefits.

7. Motivation & Opportunities

7.1 Overview

Ireland must invest in EOSC node development while momentum builds at the EU level. This is a strategic opportunity to modernise national research infrastructure, strengthen Ireland’s innovation economy, and elevate its international research profile.

7.1.1 Benefit to Research Community

EOSC offers a simplified, secure, and standards-based environment for managing research data. For Irish researchers, this means easier access to European infrastructure, reduced administrative burden, and less time spent on technical compliance. Rather than requiring building bespoke solutions, researchers can rely on EOSC to support reproducibility, data sharing, and regulatory alignment, allowing them to focus on high-impact research.

Participation in node development will support Ireland to align funding and policy across government departments, creating a unified national approach to research infrastructure. This cross-departmental coordination is essential for long-term sustainability and strategic investment in digital research capabilities.

EOSC breaks down disciplinary and institutional silos by enabling seamless data and service sharing across domains and borders. This will help Irish researchers collaborate more effectively, commercialise research outputs, and engage with industry partners. It also supports upskilling and innovation in the private sector, expanding the socioeconomic impact of Irish research.

RESEARCHER NEED	CHALLENGE	HOW EOSC IRELAND COULD ADDRESS IT
SEAMLESS ACCESS TO FEDERATED EUROPEAN RESOURCES	Researchers often face fragmented access to datasets, tools, and services across Europe, requiring multiple logins, approvals, and technical workarounds.	Provide federated access to European and national datasets, tools, and services through a single platform, eliminating the need for multiple logins, approvals, and technical workarounds.
DISCOVER AND REUSE NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN DATASETS	There is no unified platform to discover Irish datasets alongside European ones, limiting data reuse and interdisciplinary collaboration.	Offer integrated data catalogues that make Irish research outputs more visible and reusable alongside European datasets, creating a unified discovery platform.

<p>RUN WORKFLOWS ACROSS DISTRIBUTED INFRASTRUCTURE</p>	<p>Running complex workflows that span institutional, national, and European compute/storage resources is technically challenging and often unsupported.</p>	<p>Enable interoperable workflows that can run seamlessly across Irish national HPC, institutional compute, and EOSC resources without technical barriers.</p>
<p>SHARE TOOLS, CODE, AND PIPELINES IN A REPRODUCIBLE WAY</p>	<p>There is limited infrastructure for sharing analytical tools and code in a way that ensures reproducibility and compliance with FAIR principles.</p>	<p>Support reproducibility through shared environments, containers, and workflow registries that ensure compliance with FAIR principles.</p>
<p>COLLABORATE ACROSS INSTITUTIONS WITH SHARED IDENTITY AND ACCESS</p>	<p>Lack of federated identity management makes it difficult for researchers to collaborate across institutions and borders without duplicating access requests.</p>	<p>Implement shared identity and access management systems that simplify collaboration across institutions and countries without duplicating access requests.</p>
<p>TRACK AND REPORT ON DATA USAGE AND COMPLIANCE</p>	<p>Researchers and institutions struggle to monitor data usage, ensure compliance with data protection regulations, and report on impact.</p>	<p>Provide compliance and monitoring tools to support GDPR, FAIR, and Open Science mandates, enabling researchers and institutions to track data usage and ensure regulatory compliance.</p>

Table 2: How EOSC can address the needs of Researchers

7.1.2 Strategic Benefit

As EU funding becomes increasingly tied to Open Research adoption, EOSC participation ensures Ireland remains competitive in a rapidly evolving research landscape. It positions Ireland to influence future EU policy, attract global talent, and secure investment in cutting-edge research and innovation. By acting now, Ireland can shape the development of EOSC to meet national needs, while ensuring its research community is fully integrated into the European and global open science ecosystem.

Further, establishing compliant procurement and commercialisation pathways lays a foundation for standards-based cross-sector collaboration, to deliver measurable socioeconomic impact aligned with national strategies such as Impact 2030. By bridging technical, administrative, and legislative gaps between research, government and industry, in addition to those between researchers, the EOSC Node will catalyse infrastructure development and interoperability across data silos, while aligning with broader EU and national infrastructure initiatives such as HPC. This positions Ireland to not only meet FAIR data standards, but to do so in a way that is visible, valuable, and actionable, addressing the priorities of multiple government departments and agencies.

7.1.3 Timeliness

As planning progresses for the next phase of the EOSC Federation build-up (Wave 2), it is no longer sufficient for countries to simply onboard services onto an existing node. Instead, research infrastructures that wish to contribute to the EOSC Federation are expected to develop a national EOSC Node that actively contributes to the Federation. This means Ireland must not only build a node capable of integrating with the broader EOSC infrastructure but also one that offers value back to the Federation.

A fully functional EOSC Ireland Node must therefore be two-way by design: it should provide access to Irish services and data for the wider European research community, while also being capable of onboarding and supporting services developed by other organisations, both domestic and international. This reciprocal model ensures interoperability, fosters collaboration, and reinforces the federated nature of EOSC—where each node is both a contributor and a beneficiary.

Fig 5: Interconnectivity of EOSC nodes (Adapted from Digital meets Culture, 2025)²³

7.2 Alignment with National Research Strategy

7.2.1 Impact 2030: Ireland’s Research and Innovation Strategy

²³ [EOSC Federation: Architecture and Federating Capabilities: Concept Paper](#)

*Impact 2030*²⁴ outlines a strong policy agenda for Ireland as an international leader in Open Research.

Open Research falls under Pillars Two and Five of *Impact 2030*. As a cornerstone of good research practice, it supports the quality and impact of Irish research in an All-Island, EU and Global Citizenship context²⁵, as well as linking to broader objectives relating to the European Pact for Research & Innovation, the European Research Area Policy Agenda and Horizon Europe.

The below table details the alignment between the vision set out by *Impact 2030* and Ireland's participation in EOSC:

VALUE ADDED OF EOSC PARTICIPATION	ALIGNMENT WITH IMPACT 2030	RELEVANT PILLAR
STRENGTHENING RESEARCH OUTPUTS	Enhances quality and impact by access to infrastructures	Pillar 1: Maximising the Impact of Research and Innovation
ATTRACTING TALENT AND INVESTMENT	Ireland as a hub for Open Science, attracting researchers	Pillar 4: Talent at the Heart of the Ecosystem
EXPANDING ACCESS TO RESEARCH RESOURCES	Access to datasets, tools and expertise, fostering excellence	Pillar 2: Impact of Structures on Outcomes
INCREASING RESEARCH VISIBILITY AND CITATIONS	Improved accessibility leading to citations and impact	Pillar 1: Maximising the Impact of Research and Innovation
IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS FOR EU FUNDING	Alignment with Open Science to secure EU research funding.	Pillar 5: All-Island, EU and Global Connectivity
FACILITATING INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION	Strengthens European ties and cross-border research	Pillar 5: All-Island, EU and Global Connectivity
ENHANCING DATA SHARING AND INTEROPERABILITY	Standards for interdisciplinary research and data exchange	Pillar 2: Impact of Structures on Outcomes
INFLUENCING EUROPEAN	Ensuring Irish contribution and	Pillar 5: All-Island, EU and

²⁴ [Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy](#)

²⁵ [Global Citizens 2030](#)

RESEARCH POLICY	representation	Global Connectivity
------------------------	----------------	---------------------

Table 3: How EOSC aligns with IMPACT 2030

7.2.2 Research Innovation & Impact and Upskilling

Open Research is an enabler for *Impact 2030* Pillar 1 ‘RI&I and Upskilling’. The EOSC Ireland node will provide a platform to connect across the national enterprise and innovation landscape. It will facilitate and augment outcomes from the c. €1bn direct DFHERIS funding in these two key areas, by drawing on and contributing to the greater market in line with EOSC.²⁶

The Irish EOSC Node will strengthen links between Research Ireland centres, Enterprise Ireland gateways, and industry by supporting co-funded research and driving economic impact. It will serve as a trusted technical hub for EU-level access and authentication, offering a streamlined platform to promote institutional spinouts and connect enterprises with a wide range of current and emerging data-centric services.

Irish higher education institutions have demonstrated support for services on the EOSC node through their active commitment to initiatives such as IRL-DataSpaces²⁷ and the development of an IRLDAT production service, building on the NORF-funded pilot²⁸. They are also playing a key role in onboarding staff and researchers to the new EOSC EU Node, reinforcing Ireland’s engagement with the broader EOSC ecosystem. The establishment of the EOSC Ireland Node will consolidate and accelerate these efforts, providing a national platform for upskilling, service integration, and strategic alignment.

7.2.3 Digitalisation

Research and innovation are being reshaped by digital transformation, with increasing demands for secure data access, reproducibility, responsible AI integration, and high-quality data governance. The EOSC Ireland Node will be a key enabler in this shift.

EOSC Ireland is part of the digital transition of *Impact 2030*, of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) theme ‘Data, Computing and eInfrastructures’²⁹, and of Horizon Europe’s Digital Pillar.

Specifically, cross-thematic planning around funding priorities for Digital in FP10 is led through Cluster 4³⁰, which is increasingly focused on cross-cutting digital priorities such as connected collaborative computing, edge-to-cloud infrastructure, AI foundations, digital sovereignty, and compliant innovation. These priorities intersect with other ESFRI thematic areas and are deeply

²⁶ [Why EOSC is Pivotal to European Competitiveness](#)

²⁷ [Kannan, V., Wilson, N., Desplat, J.-C., Kenny, E., O’Neill, J., Sabatino, R., & Wearren, G. \(2024\). IRL-DataSpace & IRL-DSSC Position Paper A Common Data Space & Support Centre for Ireland.](#)

²⁸ [Skelton, P. & Clarke, F. \(2023\). NORF-IRLDAT project: the design and building of a pilot national data storage solution for active research data.](#)

²⁹ [ESFRI Landscape Analysis 2024](#)

³⁰ [Horizon Europe: Work Programme 2025 Digital, Industry and Space](#)

relevant to Ireland's higher education and public infrastructure development. They also underpin national strategies such as the Open Data Strategy, the National Climate Services Framework, and Ireland's participation in international research collaborations like ESA and CERN.

Meeting these demands has led to a surge in requirements for advanced IT infrastructure across Irish HEIs, including on-premises systems, institutional and national data centres, cloud services, and high-capacity network. Currently, Ireland is a member of only 13 of the over 40 ESFRI programmes: there is substantial scope for continued development, with overarching RIs still needed in economically critical areas such as health and food.

Within this evolving landscape, the EOSC Ireland Node will provide a trusted, standards-based platform that supports not only technical integration but also the governance frameworks necessary to ensure data quality, compliance, and interoperability. It will enable Ireland to contribute meaningfully to EU-wide data spaces and research infrastructures, while also addressing national needs in economically critical sectors such as health, food, and climate.

7.2.4 The National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030

The National commitment to Open Research is articulated in the goals and actions set forth in Ireland's *National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030*³¹. This builds on national policies and international recommendations including the *National Principles on Open Access* (2012), the *European Commission Recommendation on Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information* (2018), the *National Framework on the Transition to an Open Science Research Environment* (2018), and the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* (2021). It aligns with the ambitions of the European Commission (EC) in relation to Open Research and strengthening connections to international infrastructures supporting Open Research, particularly EOSC.

Ireland's National Open Research Forum promotes active engagement with EOSC by supporting the contribution of Irish infrastructures and datasets to the EOSC platform, promoting EOSC resources, and supporting Irish researchers and institutions to use EOSC's system of federated data and services. By responding to this recommendation, Ireland will ensure the relevance of its Open Research developments and competitiveness of Irish research.

7.2.5 Open Data Strategy 2023 - 2027

Ireland's *Open Data Strategy 2023–2027*³² goals for public sector data are aligned with EOSC goals for research sector data.

The *Open Data Strategy 2023–2027* sets out Ireland's commitment to improving access to high-quality government data. It aims to foster transparency, build public trust, and drive innovation. The strategy is based on three core principles:

1. strong data governance

³¹ [National Action Plan for Open Research](#)

³² [Open Data Strategy 2023 – 2027](#).

- 2. open by design and default
- 3. releasing data to support innovation

It underscores the role of Open Data in enhancing public services, boosting productivity, and building public trust. the strategy also aligns with the *European Commission’s Open Data Directive*³³ and the *Implementing Act on High Value Datasets*³⁴, ensuring legal compliance and encouraging collaboration across public bodies.

The table below outlines the alignment between EOSC and the Open Data Strategy across five areas of strategic priority:

	OPEN DATA STRATEGY	EOSC	STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT
SCOPE	Public Sector Data	Research & Scientific Data	Both contribute to a FAIR data ecosystem
PURPOSE	Increase transparency, innovation, and public service efficiency	Facilitate open science, research collaboration, and data reuse	Shared vision of open access to high-quality data
FAIR PRINCIPLES	Strongly emphasised	Core foundation	Harmonised data management standards
EU PRIORITIES	Implements the Open Data Directive and High-Value Datasets Act	Key initiative under the European Research Area and Digital Europe	Both support the European Data Space
INFRASTRUCTURE	National Open Data Portal (data.gov.ie)	Federated European infrastructure	Technical and semantic interoperability

Table 4: How EOSC aligns with the Open Data Strategy

8. Conclusion

The development of an EOSC Ireland node represents a transformative opportunity to align Ireland’s national research infrastructure with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation. This alignment is not only a technical integration—it is a strategic investment in Ireland’s future as a

³³ [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information.](#)

³⁴ [Commission Implementing Regulation \(EU\) 2023/138 of 21 December 2022 laying down a list of specific high-value datasets and the arrangements for their publication and re-use.](#)

leader in Open Science, digital research, and innovation. By establishing a national EOSC node, Ireland can streamline its research policy landscape, enhance the visibility and impact of its research outputs, and ensure that its researchers are equipped to collaborate effectively on the European and global stage.

The proposed actions and work packages outlined in this document are designed to guide a structured and inclusive transition from the preparatory phase to full implementation. They build on existing national initiatives, address critical infrastructure and governance gaps, and lay the groundwork for a sustainable, interoperable, and secure research ecosystem. Importantly, this approach reflects the EU's broader vision for digital sovereignty, FAIR data principles, and cross-border collaboration—principles that are increasingly central to research funding, policy, and practice.

To realise this vision, sustained support from the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS) will be essential. This includes not only financial investment but also leadership in stakeholder engagement, interdepartmental coordination, and capacity building across the research community. The successful implementation of EOSC Ireland will depend on the ability to deliver key technical components—such as identity and access management, registry integration, and secure data handling—as well as the establishment of clear governance structures and legal representation at the Federation level.

Moreover, the timing is critical. With Ireland set to hold the EU Presidency in the second half of 2026, there is a unique opportunity to demonstrate leadership in shaping the future of European research infrastructure. Active participation in the EOSC Federation during this period will reinforce Ireland's commitment to Open Science, strengthen its influence in EU policymaking, and support national objectives such as those outlined in *Impact 2030*.

Finally, the EOSC Ireland node is not just a technical platform; it is a catalyst for innovation, collaboration, and economic impact. It will help DFHERIS deliver upskilling and digital transformation through the research sector, enabling Irish researchers to participate fully in Horizon Europe FP10, and supporting the secondary use of health data under the European Health Data Space (EHDS). By acting now, Ireland can ensure that its research community remains competitive, connected, and at the forefront of scientific discovery in the years to come.

Appendix 1: CSA Budget

The CSA is envisaged as a 12-month Action, structured as a coordinated project across multiple stakeholder institutions.

WP TITLE	WP LEAD ORGANISATION	WP DESCRIPTION	COST CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	COST (EURO)
WP0: PROJECT MANAGEMENT & COORDINATION	HEAnet	- Project Management, Coordination, Oversight and Reporting, Budget Management	Personnel	0.5 FTE, 12 months	€50,000
			Travel & Events		€2,000
					€52,000
WP1: TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE	ICHEC	- Technical architecture, including analysis of synergies with other national initiatives and infrastructures to leverage them for a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for EOSC Ireland. - Develop a technical roadmap for EOSC Ireland highlighting how it will support continuous evolution and innovation and steps to be taken to connect research data repositories.	Personnel	1.2 FTE across 3 organisations, 8 months	€80,000
			Travel & Events	<i>may require EU travel for training/system assessment</i>	€2,500
					€82,500

WP2: TECHNICAL TRIALS	ICHEC	- Conduct technical trials/PoCs of relevant technologies, such as Research Cloud and any other deemed relevant, including integrations of external (national and institutional) services with the node.	Personnel	1.2 FTE across 3 organisations, 9 months	€90,000	
			Equipment		€6,000	
			Travel & Events		<i>may require EU travel for training/system assessment</i>	€2,500
			Other External Services		Licences, Cloud Services, consultancy	€60,000
WP3: DEFINING THE ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE	Technological University Dublin	- Determine the organisational structure for the day-to-day operations of EOSC Ireland and its governance in the longer term. - In collaboration with WG1, it will set out the types of roles that are required to develop and operate the EOSC Ireland node. - Establish a sustainable funding model with associated required costings. - Consider whether a new legal entity needs to be established. - Establish and	Personnel	1 FTE across 5 organisations, 9 months	€75,000	
			Consultancy		<i>may need financial and legal advisory regarding new entity</i>	€5,000

		test relevant legal and organisational relationships as part of the CSA			
					€80,000
WP4: TECHNICAL PLANNING FOR CONNECTING TO EOSC FEDERATION	University of Limerick	Technical planning for joining EOSC Federation	Personnel	0.6 FTE across 3 organisations, 4 months	€20,000
			Travel & Events	interorganisational, EU travel needed	€3,000
					€23,000
WP5: TECHNICAL PLANNING FOR SERVICES FOR HANDLING SENSITIVE DATA	Trinity College Dublin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical planning for connecting to services for handling sensitive data. - This will concern primarily certifications and compliances needed by an EOSC Ireland node to connect to such services hence enabling access to them from users who connect via the EOSC Ireland node 	Personnel	1 FTE across 3 organisations, 4 months	€33,333
			Travel & Events	interorganisational, EU travel needed	€2,500
					€35,833
WP6: COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT, DISSEMINATION AND TRAINING	HEAnet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Run community stakeholder engagement events. - Produce materials for dissemination. 	Personnel	0.2 FTE, 1 organisation, 12 months	€20,000
			Travel & Events		€5,500
			Materials & Consumables		€5,000

		- Setup and manage stakeholder advisory fora			
					€30,500
				<i>Budget</i>	€462,333
				<i>Overheads @ 25%</i>	€115,583
				Total Cost	€577,916

Table 5: Proposed CSA Budget

Table 6: GANTT Chart for CSA

Appendix 2: Federation build-up and expected costs of an EOSC node

During 2025 13 national and thematic initiatives are working to contribute to the EOSC federation by developing their own nodes. These are outlined in the table below and a mixture of national, scientific disciplinary (thematic) and infrastructure nodes. They were shortlisted by the EOSC governance from an initial 129 proposals.

The 13 nodes are all working to be part of the EOSC federation by the end of 2025 and a call for more nodes to be connected in 2026 is due to be issued.

ORGANISATION	COUNTRY	SCOPE
CSC	Finland	General ad thematic repositories, Competence centre, services for genomic data
CNR BLUECLOUD	Italy	Thematic RI for marine research. Data sets and VREs
NCN	Poland	Generic national infrastructure and repositories
BBMRI ERIC	International	Thematic node, data sets and resources
CERN	Switzerland	Zenodo, Indico, REANA, HepData
SURF	Netherlands	Infrastructure and thematic and academic repositories. Services for sensitive data
LSRN (ELIXIR, EMBL, INSTRUCT, BIOIMAGING)	International	Infrastructure and data resources for Life Sciences
ESRF/PANOSC	International	Infrastructure, VREs

EUDAT	International	Research Data Management services
NFDI	Germany	Federated Repositories and associated services
CNRS/DATATERRA	France	Thematic Research Infrastructure
ICSC	Italy	Infrastructure and thematic and academic repositories. Services for sensitive data
CVTI	Slovakia	Generic national infrastructure

Table 7: 13 Candidate Nodes

The 13 nodes have provided initial budgetary information related to the costs of designing, implementing and operating an EOSC node. These costs, outlined below are estimates, vary depending on size and scope of each node and are to be re-assessed at the end of 2025 when more experience with connecting to the EOSC federation is gained. Costs for connecting nodes to the EOSC federation will be assessed at the end of 2025. The estimated average five-year cost of designing, implementing and operation a node is therefore in the order of €9.8M.

	AVERAGE	MIN	MAX
DESIGN OF A NODE (EQUIVALENT TO THE CSA PROPOSED IN THIS PAPER)	0.83 M	0.25M	2M
IMPLEMENTING A NODE	1.5M	0.6M	2.7M
OPERATING A NODE	0.9M/year	0.13M/year	2.15M/year
ONGOING DEVELOPMENT/EXPANSION OF A NODE	0.6M/year	0.3M/year	0.8M/year
CONNECTING A NODE TO THE EOSC FEDERATION	TBD	TBD	TBD

Table 8: Estimated average five-year cost of designing, implementing and operation a node

Appendix 3: National, Institutional and Thematic Infrastructures and Services

Shared services are essential for delivering efficient, centralised access to research resources. While thematic and institutional services foster collaboration within specific communities, their aggregation through platforms like the EOSC Ireland node and HPC ensures broader access to critical infrastructure such as data storage, HPC, and research tools. By leveraging and aligning existing services, EOSC Ireland can reduce duplication, optimise resource use, and enhance the overall efficiency of Ireland’s research ecosystem.

This approach supports Open Research principles and aligns with national strategies such as *Impact 2030* and NORF, promoting a cohesive and integrated research environment. EOSC Ireland can further assist participating research infrastructures in adopting shared services—such as identity and access management, metadata and interoperability standards, workflow orchestration, and federated access—while supporting their scalability and alignment with European infrastructures.

A selection of services with potential to participate in EOSC Ireland is outlined below. However, their readiness varies and should be assessed in detail under Work Package 1. For a broader overview of Open Science progress, challenges, and support structures in Ireland, refer to the *National Open Research Landscape Report*.

National Infrastructures and Services

IRLDAT: Shared Data Storage Service Pilot

Shared Storage service for active research data, IRLDAT developed and piloted a data storage solution that enabled the sharing of research data with collaborators from different institutions, within and outside Ireland, during the active phase of research. The project was based on the use of the B2Drop service from EUDAT diverse user groups engaged in the project, which delivered the definition of a national production service, along with costs and recommendations for sustainability. Funding for a production service has been approved, and the service will become operational at a national level in 2025.

IRL-DataSpaces & IRL-DSSC (Common Data Spaces for Ireland)

A data space is an interoperable framework, based on common governance principles, standards, practices and enabling services, that enables trusted data transactions between participants³⁵. EOSC is one of the several Common European Data Spaces.

³⁵[Data Spaces Support Centre Glossary](#)

The common European data spaces ecosystem

Since October 2023, ICHEC and HEAnet have been collaborating on the development of IRL-DataSpace, a national Common Data Space designed to support Ireland’s Open Data Strategy. It aims to enable academic, public sector, and industry stakeholders to access and use data for research, innovation, and evidence-based policymaking. This work is detailed in the IRL-DataSpace Position Paper.

To support this vision, ICHEC and HEAnet are also working to establish the IRL Data Space Support Centre (IRL-DSSC), which will coordinate stakeholder engagement and co-development efforts. Together, IRL-DataSpace and IRL-DSSC focus on creating a federated, FAIR-aligned, high-performance data ecosystem with shared governance, robust digital infrastructure, and professional support services.

EOSC Ireland will interoperate with IRL-DataSpace to ensure seamless discovery and sharing of research resources across both federations. While the exact mechanisms for integration are still to be defined, the complementary nature of the two initiatives supports the current vision of joint leadership by HEAnet and ICHEC, leveraging their roles as national digital infrastructure providers.

Fig 6: The Common European Data Spaces

Institutional Infrastructures and Services

Institutions across Ireland have individual levels of infrastructure and services available, here we use University College Dublin (UCD) as one example.

UCD’s strategy focusses on delivering integrated supports across UCD campuses nationally and internationally, to enable groundbreaking research that has clear impact at scale on the defining issues of our time, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), One Health and Societal Transformations. UCD Research IT is subscribed to the IRLDAT production service for active storage and sharing, is running its own Dropbox commercial store and share pilot, has recently completed hardware upgrades to its Sonic HPC/GPU service, and is onboarding UCD to the OCRE 2024 Framework. UCD uses and provides cloud research and teaching resources through Microsoft and Google. UCD data centre hosts substantial storage and processing infrastructure that supports UCD AI institute, CeADAR, and

National Climate Services Framework provision with Met Eireann and ESA, key national cultural heritage collections, and major thematic infrastructures such as Vulcan. Its constituent schools organise distributed thematic infrastructures and access. Mediated and managed by UCD RIT, and subject to appropriate due diligence, the EOSC Ireland node will help UCD to organise and aggregate all-campus access its resources. UCD expects this to provide a secure, compliant and scalable environment that supports digitalisation of Irish research and the learning experience and is conducive to economic development through open science aligned with UCD strategy.

Thematic Infrastructures and Services

Digital Repository of Ireland

The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a CoreTrustSeal-certified national infrastructure dedicated to the long-term preservation and access of Ireland's social, cultural, and humanities digital data. It is the coordinating organisation for the NORF, which drives the open research agenda in Ireland. EOSC Ireland could, for example, integrate with DRI for data preservation and FAIR data sharing.

DRI serves multiple functions:

- **Digital Preservation:** Ensures ongoing access to fragile digital content.
- **Open Access & FAIR Principles:** Promotes findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data.
- **Training & Support:** Offers digital preservation training and support, including for underfunded community organisations.
- **Research Collaboration:** Engages in national and European-funded research projects, including partnerships with Europeana and the Research Data Alliance 2.

ISSDA

The Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA), based at University College Dublin, is Ireland's leading national service for the acquisition, preservation, and dissemination of quantitative social science data. It plays a critical role in supporting evidence-based research by providing access to high-quality datasets on Irish society, economy, and public policy. ISSDA is also Ireland's national service provider to the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA), aligning Irish data infrastructure with European standards and enabling participation in international comparative research. In the context of EOSC Ireland, ISSDA can serve as a key thematic data infrastructure, particularly for the social sciences. Integration with EOSC Ireland would allow ISSDA-hosted datasets to be discoverable and accessible through the EOSC portal.

DARIAH-IE

DARIAH-IE, the Irish national node of the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH ERIC), plays a pivotal role in supporting digitally enabled research in the arts and humanities across Ireland. Coordinated through the Research Ireland, DARIAH-IE connects Irish scholars to a pan-European network that fosters collaboration, digital tool development, and training in computational methods. It supports a wide range of activities including digital curation, data

management, and interdisciplinary research, while also contributing to national policy discussions on research infrastructure. As part of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), DARIAH-IE ensures that Irish arts and humanities researchers are aligned with European standards and practices in Open Science and digital scholarship ¹.

EOSC Ireland can integrate with DARIAH-IE by incorporating its tools, services, and datasets into the EOSC service catalogue, thereby enhancing discoverability and reuse across disciplines. This integration would not only strengthen Ireland's contribution to EOSC but also ensure that the arts and humanities are fully represented in national and European digital research infrastructures.

iCRAG

iCRAG is the Research Ireland Research Centre in applied geosciences hosted by the School of Earth Sciences, University College Dublin, the largest Geoscience School in Ireland. iCRAG aims to deliver extensive, integrated research on the earth system to facilitate environmentally sustainable development of the earth resources required for decarbonized economies, and to promote understanding of how people react to and manage our relationship with the earth. iCRAG is at the heart of Irish geoscience data: linking public and commercial entities; deep earth deep time data use and production, transformation and processing, recovery and storage³⁶.

UCD School of Earth Sciences is building the Caldera private cloud with browser-based access and associated storage and GPU compute for windows users to process and visualise 3/4D datasets with commercially licenced software. iCRAG is developing a national geodata research repository built on PostGIS and Docker, and spatial metadata harmonisation for interoperability of geodatasets with Geological Survey Ireland, and so the EU level geo-data spaces. It has been instrumental in developing an IRLDAT use case for ICHEC hosting, leading to the present production service to which UCD is subscribed. iCRAG@UCD has helped prototype the mechanisms of the EOSC-node, as the customer in an EOSC-Future funded contract SER-23-131 between UCD, Géant and the Irish SME Geochron Ltd., for commercial provision of synthetic Lidar and Radiometric datasets from quarries around Ireland in support of Ireland's implementation of the EU Basic Safety Standard for Radioactivity. iCRAG is supporting development of HPC through the EuroCC2 digital flagship project Earth:Chec³⁷, which will lay the groundwork for iCRAG and SES deployments on the EOSC Ireland node.

EOSC Ireland could integrate with iCRAG by federating access to its datasets, analytical tools, and research outputs, making them discoverable and reusable across the European Open Science Cloud. This would enhance the visibility and impact of Irish geoscience research while aligning iCRAG's data practices with FAIR and Open Science principles. Furthermore, iCRAG's experience in cross-sectoral partnerships positions it as a valuable contributor to EOSC Ireland's mission of bridging research and enterprise through digital integration.

ELIXIR Ireland

³⁶ [Research Data Management and Processing for an Irish Geoscience Research Centre and its Stakeholders.](#)

³⁷ [Earth:Chec](#)

ELIXIR Ireland is the national node of the European ELIXIR infrastructure, which supports life science research by coordinating bioinformatics resources across Europe. Based at University College Dublin and involving multiple Irish universities and research centres, ELIXIR Ireland plays a central role in enabling the storage, analysis, and integration of large-scale biological data, including genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics. It supports key areas such as personalised medicine, systems biology, and computational modelling of diseases. ELIXIR Ireland also provides training, data standards, and technical services to ensure that biomedical data is managed in a transparent, reproducible, and FAIR-compliant manner.

EOSC Ireland could integrate with ELIXIR Ireland by federating access to its bioinformatics tools, workflows, and datasets, making them available through the EOSC Federation. This would enhance cross-disciplinary research by enabling life science data to be combined with environmental, social, and clinical datasets. This integration would ensure that Ireland's life sciences research remains at the forefront of global biomedical innovation.

GDI-Ireland

Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) Ireland is the national component of a Europe-wide initiative aimed at integrating genomics into healthcare and advancing personalised medicine. Co-led by University College Dublin (UCD), the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI), and FutureNeuro, GDI Ireland is jointly funded by the European Commission and the Health Research Board (HRB). It supports the secure management and federated analysis of Irish genomic data, enabling researchers to collaborate across borders while safeguarding personal data. GDI Ireland contributes to the broader 1+ Million Genomes initiative, which seeks to build a federated network of national genome collections to accelerate biomedical research and the development of treatments for diseases such as cancer.

EOSC Ireland could integrate with GDI Ireland by providing the federated infrastructure needed to support secure, cross-border access to genomic and clinical data

The GDI Ireland³⁸ (GDI-IE) project is the Irish arm of the wider European initiative. One of the outputs of GDI-IE is to create a long-term sustainability plan for the Irish infrastructure. This includes but is not limited to establishing a storage mechanism and secure processing environment (SPE) for human genomic data in Ireland. Genomics data will be part of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) from 2031.

International Infrastructures and Services

European Health Data Space (EHDS)

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) is a landmark EU initiative aimed at enabling the secure, efficient use of health data across Europe for both clinical care (primary use) and research, innovation, and policymaking (secondary use). In Ireland, the HealthData@IE project - led by the

³⁸ [Genomic Data Infrastructure \(GDI\) Ireland](#)

Department of Health in partnership with HIQA and the Health Research Board - is laying the foundation for EHDS implementation. This includes the development of a Health Data Access Body (HDAB), a secure processing environment, a national health metadata catalogue, and a data access application system. Together, these components will ensure that anonymised health data can be accessed under strict governance and security protocols.

EOSC Ireland can play a vital enabling role by integrating with EHDS-aligned infrastructures like HealthData@IE. Through EOSC's federated architecture, Ireland's health data assets could become discoverable and interoperable with European datasets, supporting cross-disciplinary research in genomics, public health, and the social sciences. This integration would not only ensure compliance with EU standards but also position Ireland as a key contributor to European and global health research.

ESFRI Research Infrastructures and their Critical Role in EOSC

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) has played a central role in shaping Europe's research landscape, fostering world-class infrastructures that provide not only scientific facilities but also high-quality data, advanced tools, and essential services. As the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) evolves, ESFRI RIs are expected to form the backbone of its thematic nodes, contributing domain-specific expertise, data stewardship, and community engagement.

Ireland is an active participant in several key ESFRI RIs through its national outstations - also referred to as nodes - which represent significant national investment and are already delivering impactful services to the research community. Notable examples include ELIXIR-Ireland, DARIAH-Ireland, and the Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA).

The establishment of EOSC Ireland will provide a vital, unifying framework that coordinates diverse national service offerings—including those from ESFRI nodes and other research-performing organisations—into the EOSC Federation, thereby maximising the return on investment in Irish ESFRI RI memberships, harmonising technical standards, sharing best practices, and developing a unified national strategy for engagement with the broader EOSC ecosystem.

EOSC Ireland will accelerate Irish scientific discovery by:

Uniting Irish scientific research infrastructure

Sharing expertise and domain agnostic resources

Enabling more (cross-)domain FAIR & Open research projects

Fig 7: The benefits of EOSC to consolidate Irish ESFRI Research Infrastructures and other research organisations

[A full list of ESFRI Research Infrastructures is available here.](#)

The following table outlines Irish membership of the ESFRI RIs:

ESFRI Research Infrastructure	Domain	Ireland's Membership Status	EOSC Cluster
ACTRIS	Environment	Member	ENVRI-FAIR
CESSDA-ERIC	Social & Cultural Innovation	Member (via ISSDA)	SSHOC
CTAO	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Member	ESCAPE
DARIAH-ERIC	Social & Cultural Innovation	Member (via DARIAH-IE)	SSHOC
ECRIN-ERIC	Biological & Medical Sciences	Member (via HRB-NCTO)	EOSC-Life
ELIXIR	Biological & Medical Sciences	Member (via ELIXIR-Ireland)	EOSC-Life
ELT	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Member (through ESO)	ESCAPE
EMBL	Life sciences	Member	EOSC-Life
EMSO-ERIC	Environment	Member (via Marine Institute)	ENVRI-FAIR
ESS	Social & Cultural Innovation / Health	Member	SSHOC
EU-IBISBA	Biological & Medical Sciences	Member (via UCC)	EOSC-Life
EURO-ARGO ERIC	Environment	Member	ENVRI-FAIR
GUIDE	Social & Cultural Innovation	Member, Co-coordinated by Ireland (UCD)	SSHOC
HL-LHC	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Access through CERN membership	ESCAPE
ICOS-ERIC	Environment	Observer	ENVRI-FAIR
ISBE	Biological & Medical Sciences	Member	EOSC-Life
MARINERG-i	Energy	Coordinated by Ireland (MaREI, UCC)	PANOSC
PRACE	Data, Computing & Digital RIs	Member (via ICHEC)	PANOSC

Table 9: Ireland's engagement with ESFRI RIs

Appendix 4: Broader National Context

This section explores the broader national Open Research landscape relevant to EOSC Ireland. Open Research is a national and international policy agenda encompassing open access to research publications; research data and other outputs that are findable, accessible, interoperable and machine readable (FAIR); infrastructures for access to and preservation of research; skills and competencies; research assessment reform, and more.

The Center for Open Science's strategy for culture and behaviour change³⁹ requires five levels of intervention represented by the pyramid below. These levels are progressive, reflecting the fact that successful implementation of higher levels depends on successful implementation of lower levels.

Fig 8: COS Visualisation of strategic intervention for culture change

Infrastructure is the base of the pyramid making behaviour change possible.

We are witnessing the emergence of an ecosystem supporting the web of FAIR data in Ireland, driven by active communities, evolving policies, and targeted incentives. Key initiatives such as the Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network, Open Repositories Ireland (ORI), the Open Source Program Office (OSPO), the Responsible Use of Research Metrics (RURM) Training Module, TROPIC (Training for Open Research in an Irish Context), the National Open Access Monitor, the iFrame Research Data Management Framework, and ABOARD (Incentivising Open Research Practices in Ireland) are laying the groundwork for a culture of responsible, open, and FAIR-aligned research practices.

³⁹ [Center for Open Science Strategy for Culture Change](#)

At the infrastructure level, both national and institutional shared services and thematic research infrastructures are being developed to support this transformation. EOSC Ireland aims to provide cohesion across these efforts, bridging policy, practice, and infrastructure to create a unified, interoperable research environment.

In the broader context of Open Research, the core functions of EOSC Ireland, when integrated with these shared services and thematic infrastructures, will form the foundation of the EOSC Ireland Node. This node will be further strengthened by the networks and services that enable the web of FAIR data, ensuring that Ireland's research system is connected, collaborative, and aligned with European and global standards

The National Open Research Forum (NORF)

The National commitment to Open Research is articulated in the goals and actions set forth in Ireland's *National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030*. The launch of the Action Plan in November 2022 inaugurated an ambitious national policy designed to meet three strategic objectives by 2030:

1. to establish a culture of Open Research,
2. to achieve 100% open access to research publications,
3. and to enable FAIR research data and other outputs.

Implementation of Ireland's *National Action Plan* is being overseen by NORF⁴⁰. NORF was established in 2017 to drive the Irish agenda for Open Research.

NORF develops national objectives and coordinated actions to support Ireland's transition to Open Research, aligned with international objectives and coordinated actions to support Ireland's transition to Open Research, most recently through the National Action Plan for Open Research. Since 2022, NORF has administered the Open Research Fund, a competitive stream of funding, to deliver priority actions in the National Action Plan for Open Research and to foster uptake of Open Research in Ireland.

Services and Networks supporting the Web of FAIR Data

National Persistent Identifier Strategy and Roadmap

At the end of 2024, NORF launched Ireland's National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy: *Interoperability, Openness, and Impact – Recommendations and Roadmap for an Irish National PID Strategy*⁴¹. This report sets out recommendations and a roadmap for a national persistent identifier (PID) strategy for Ireland. PIDs are a cornerstone of a modern, digital research system. They uniquely identify entities involved in research, such as grant awards, researchers, instruments, datasets, or publications, and enable structured information about those entities to be shared.

⁴⁰ [National Action Plan for Open Research](#)

⁴¹ [Interoperability, Openness, and Impact: Recommendations and Roadmap for an Irish National PID Strategy](#).

The vision of this roadmap is of a more efficient, transparent, and open research ecosystem in Ireland, one in which information flows more easily between systems and organisations, bureaucratic burdens are reduced, and research transparency and integrity are enhanced. PIDs underpin this vision because they act as bridges between systems, provide a rich information resource to reduce time-consuming and error-prone manual data entry, and can be used to automate processes and to demonstrate connections between entities, such as a grant and a dataset.

The importance of PIDs in EOSC is also recognised in the Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁴². It defines a set of expectations about what persistent identifiers will be used to support a functioning environment of FAIR research.

Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network

Sonraí⁴³ aims to enable the development of data stewardship skills across the national research landscape through raising the profile data stewards, greater recognition of the need for data stewardship, professionalisation of the role of data steward and skills, and knowledge development throughout the emerging community. By developing these skills nationally, we can ensure the curation, preservation and dissemination of our national data assets, and the continued growth and development of our FAIR data landscape.

Open Repositories Ireland

Open Repositories Ireland (ORI)⁴⁴ is a new membership organisation dedicated to advancing Open Research practices and repository services across Ireland. ORI promotes, supports, and develops open repositories and repository staff through networking, training, and advocacy.

Led by the University of Galway, the network brings together a consortium of fourteen institutional and organisational partners to enhance Ireland's open repository landscape.

Open-Source Program Office (OSPO)

Open-source software, shared workflows foster transparent, collaborative, and sustainable software development of FAIR data and software. Ireland hosts two leading Open-Source Program Offices (OSPO), at LERO (University of Limerick) and at Trinity College Dublin, both members of CURIOS the global Community of University and Research Institution OSPOs. OSPOs promote onboarding, interoperability, and resource sharing for federated, FAIR, and open science. LERO's OSPO is a partner in the EOSC-OSCARS mTess program, that will make over 500 RDM related training materials, best practices in cloud workflows (workflowhub.eu), and training materials on open-source software, visible and discoverable in EOSC.

Other relevant national initiatives:

⁴² [A Persistent Identifier \(PID\) policy for the European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#)

⁴³ [Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network](#)

⁴⁴ [Open Repositories Ireland](#)

- TROPIC (TRaining for OPen research in an Irish Context)⁴⁵
- National Open Access Monitor⁴⁶
- iFrame Research Data Management Framework
- Incentivising Open Research Practices in Ireland (ABOARD⁴⁷)

⁴⁵ [TROPIC](#)

⁴⁶ [National Open Access Monitor](#)

⁴⁷ [ABOARD project](#)

Appendix 5: A Usage Case for EOSC

QuarryLink, a federated edge-to-cloud data pathway for industrial-academic collaboration

The QuarryLink Use Case offers a real-world demonstration of how federated research infrastructures can effectively bridge the gap between academic research, industrial needs, and public digital services. Originating from a live industrial site in County Cork, it will showcase how sensor-rich environments such as quarries and ports can produce high-value data streams. These can unlock meaningful insights for research, policy development, and innovation.

The use case will leverage key pillars of the EOSC Ireland node:

- **Federated Data Governance:** Through the application of site-specific governance protocols, registered and catalogued within the EOSC Ireland Node (e.g. iCAT) this Use Case will explore the practicalities of ensuring compliance, traceability and trust across diverse data providers and consumers within a federated environment.
- **FAIR Data at Source:** By enabling data to be discoverable and interoperable at the Edge of the site, the use case will investigate best practices for implementing FAIR principles across the Edge-Fog-Cloud continuum. The cross-cutting approach, spanning industry and academia, has the potential to offer valuable insights for shaping FAIR-aligned methodologies within the EOSC Ireland node.
- **In-Place Compute Efficiency:** Instead of transmitting large industrial or academic datasets across networks, this UC will explore how computational workflow can be brought closer to where the data resides – be that at the Edge, on Fog nodes, or within trusted HPC environments like ICHEC. Aligning with the principles of federated computing, the aim is to evaluate strategies where processing is selectively deployed near data sources or storage nodes, minimising data-movement, improving energy-efficiency, and enhancing data sovereignty. This approach supports EOSC goals for secure, efficient, sustainable, and scalable data handling.
- **Reusable Toolchains and Open Collaboration:** Through the development of containerised, FAIR-registered analysis tools, the use case will explore how discoverable workbench-containers will empower other researchers, institutions, and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to reuse workflows, boosting the utility and impact of the EOSC Ireland infrastructure.

The goal of the use case will be to demonstrate a repeatable model for how a national EOSC Node can serve as a bridge between national research cloud infrastructure and the growing demand for trusted industrial–academic data collaboration.

The 4-Step Data Lifecycle

Fig 9: Visualisation of the QuarryLink use case

1. Edge-to-Fog Data Capture & Governance Initiation

At an industrial site in County Cork, a range of ground-based sensors generate continuous environmental and operational data. This data is transmitted from the Edge Layer to a local Fog Layer node, powered by a compact iRODS server. Here, the system performs sensor data aggregation, device-level orchestration, and enforces local data governance protocols. These protocols define how data is managed, classified, and shared within and beyond the site.

2. Federation with the National EOSC Node

The aggregated sensor data and the associated governance policies are both iCAT-registered and federated with the EOSC Ireland node. Data is then securely transferred to an EOSC-compliant Public Cloud storage facility in Cork City. Based on its classification, data is catalogued as either:

- Open and discoverable via FAIR metadata, or
- Restricted due to sensitivity, with access tightly controlled through federated identity and governance mechanisms.

3. Collaborative Open Toolchain Development via TUS

Researchers at the Technological University of the Shannon (TUS) in Limerick, connected to the EOSC Ireland node federation via their own iRODS server, collaborate with the industrial site to co-develop a containerised software workbench. This toolset is designed to analyse the Open Data portion of the industrial dataset. Like the data it operates on, the containerised workbench

and its associated governance protocols are iCAT-registered, enabling FAIR discoverability and reuse by other researchers or industry partners within the EOSC Federation.

4. In-Place Federated HPC Compute via ICHEC

Using the EOSC Ireland node federation, TUS researchers request HPC resources from ICHEC, which is also a federated node participant. Crucially, the data remains securely in the EOSC Public Cloud - computation is brought to the data to ensure data residency, reduce transmission overhead, and maintain compliance with access policies

Once processing is complete, the results are returned to the TUS iRODS instance. Depending on the derived data's governance classification, it is either:

- Published as Open Data within the EOSC Ireland Node, or
- Shared privately with the industrial partner under the same federated access structure.

Appendix 6: Other EOSC national nodes

There are many examples of similar initiatives in other European countries, which are already production services and ready to contribute to the EOSC federation at European level. This is happening as part of the EOSC Federation's build-up phase. From an initial 120 proposals 13 Candidate EOSC Nodes have been invited to contribute to the first wave deployment of the EOSC Federation.

Several commonalities can be identified among these Candidate Nodes⁴⁸:

- Many of the anticipated nodes are planning to contribute to the EOSC Federation via an incremental approach. They will begin with resources that are easier to federate to test as soon as possible a prototype of the Federation that can bring benefits to researchers in the short term.
- In most cases the Candidate Nodes are anticipating providing the Federation with a mix of general-purpose and domain-specific resources.
- Most Candidate Nodes already have a compatible Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure (AAI), as well as monitoring, helpdesk and accounting capabilities ready to be federated.
- Overall, the Candidate Nodes identified more than 60 possible use cases that could be considered for implementation, and it is evident that many of those use cases rely on data visitation, data transfer and sensitive data cross-node workflows implementations.

EOSC Finland

CSC - IT Center for Science⁴⁹ is contributing to the EOSC Federation by building up a national node for Finland. The node will be built in collaboration with the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture, the national Open Science Coordination and other national stakeholders that will be gradually engaged (and onboarded in the national node) via the EOSC Finnish Forum mechanism⁵⁰.

The EOSC Finland Node will unlock access to national FAIR data, data services and research data management competence development. These resources will be accessible via a user-friendly entry point. The node will be accessible for Finnish researchers via the Haka federation, and it will be integrated with MyAccessID and EOSC AAI. The datasets, data services and training resources will be discoverable via the EOSC federated service catalogue.

Through coordination with the LUMI AI Factory the national EOSC node will provide access to unique and large datasets and will also pilot a cross-node use cases on secure processing environments. As CSC is the main contractor of the EuroHPC Federation (EuroFP) tender, CSC will also promote interoperability between the EOSC Federation and the EuroFP.

⁴⁸ [The EOSC Federation's build-up phase is underway](#)

⁴⁹ [CSC – IT Center for Science](#)

⁵⁰ [EOSC Forum Finland](#)

Main Goals

- Making Finnish FAIR datasets, services and research data management (RDM) trainings discoverable in the EOSC Federation (examples of national services are: fairdata.fi; research.fi; national data infrastructures and RI national nodes (e.g. FinCLARIN); etc.)
- Making available unique, large size or restricted access datasets via interoperability with the LUMI AI factory
- Making sensitive data discoverable and through authorisation accessible in a secure processing environment (for example in collaboration with EUDAT, ELIXIR, SURF)
- Making the EOSC Finland node interoperable with EuroFP and the LUMI AI factory
- Providing all the necessary core federating capabilities towards the EOSC Federation
- Contributing to the interoperability framework and joint concept model development

Needs addressed

- FAIR supporting user-centric services that facilitate the research process
- RDM competence development
- Availability of unique, large size and restricted datasets
- Integrating federating capabilities

Key Benefits

- Demonstrating the value of a national node for the EOSC Federation as a whole and for the country
- Increasing discovery and availability of FAIR data and FAIR supporting services
- Testing interoperability between EuroFP and EOSC Federation
- Bringing the EOSC Federation close to the private sector and their RDI collaboration with research performing organisations thanks to the connection with the LUMI AI factory

Who Benefits

- European researchers who can access Finnish datasets, services and RDM training resources on top of the other resources made available through the EOSC Federation
- European researchers and businesses that can access large size or restricted datasets
- European researchers who need to access and process sensitive data
- Finnish organisations willing to contribute to the EOSC Federation via a national node
- Stakeholders that will benefit from the integration of the EOSC Finland node in the LUMI AI factory ecosystem

<https://ri-portfolio.esfri.eu/ri-portfolio/table/>

Glossary of Terms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure. Edugate is an implementation of AAI, HEAnet's federated single sign-on (SSO) service.
CESSDA	CESSDA - the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences.
Data Space	A distributed system defined by a governance framework, that enables trustworthy data transactions between participants while supporting trust and data sovereignty [https://dataspacesupportcentre.refined.site/space/Glossary/176554052/2.+Core+Concepts]
DRI	The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a certified trusted digital repository that provides long-term preservation and access to Ireland's humanities, cultural heritage, and social sciences data.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC EU Node	The EOSC EU Node is the first node in the EOSC Federation, launched in April 2024 by the European Commission.
EOSC Federation	The EOSC Federation aims to provide Europe's researchers with the necessary digital resources to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders according to the principles of FAIR data and open science, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.
EOSC Ireland	EOSC Ireland is a digital platform that connects research infrastructures across Ireland to the European-wide EOSC Federation.
EOSC Node	An EOSC Node will be typically formed by multiple research institutes, universities and other stakeholders with a common geographical (European, regional or national) or thematic scope.
EOSC OSCARS	OSCARS (Open Science Clusters Action for Research and Society) is a four-year Horizon Europe project that fosters Open Science with thematic areas Humanities and Social Sciences, Life Sciences, Environmental Sciences, Photon and Neutron Science, Astronomy, Nuclear and Particle Physics.
ERA	The European Research Area is the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU.

ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ELIXIR	ELIXIR is an intergovernmental EU organization that brings together life science data infrastructure. Its platforms include databases, software tools, training materials, cloud storage, and compute. Established in 2013, it started its fourth 5-year cycle in 2024. https://elixir-europe.org/
FAIR	FAIR data are data which meet the FAIR data principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. These principles have been widely adopted by researchers, research performing organisations and research funding organisations, including the European Commission.
GDI	Genomic Data Infrastructure for the 1+ Million Genomes program, that supports federated sharing and analysis of EU genome data. Coordinated by ELIXIR
HEAnet	HEAnet is Ireland's National Research and Education Network, delivering high-speed internet connectivity and ICT shared services to all levels of the Irish education sector.
ICHEC	The Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC) at the University of Galway is Ireland's national centre for High-Performance Computing (HPC) providing e-infrastructure, services and expertise to academia, industry and the public sector supported by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Skills and the Higher Education Authority.
IRLDAT	IRLDAT is a project funded under the 2022 Open Research Fund to develop a national shared data storage service for active data, starting with a pilot for a small number of research groups with the aim to grow the service into a national service
IRL-DataSpace	A Common Data Space for Ireland to address data-driven global challenges through collaborative research and innovation between academia, industry, and the public sector.
IRL-DSSC	Data Space Support Centre for Ireland, engaging stakeholders across the community for participation and co-development.
ISSDA	The Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA) is Ireland's leading centre for quantitative data acquisition, preservation, and dissemination. Based at UCD Library, its mission is to ensure access to quantitative datasets in the social sciences, and to advance the promotion of international comparative studies of the Irish economy and Irish society.
National	A National Open Access Monitoring action of the NORF 2022 Open Research Fund

Open Access Monitor	to develop a monitor for open access at the national level, initially through pilot reports and a national dashboard to publish, analyse and track progress towards 100% open access, led by IReL.
NORF	The National Open Research Forum was established in 2017 to drive the Irish agenda for Open Research and is funded by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research and Innovation and Science through the Higher Education Authority (HEA).
PID	Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are long-lasting, globally unique identifiers for people (researchers), places (research organisations), and things (research outputs and grants).
RI	Research Infrastructure. In general, RI refers to equipment, services, human resources researchers avail of to conduct and support their research. In the context of EOOSC, RI refers primarily to digital infrastructure and services complemented by human resources.
SURF Research Cloud	A cloud-based portal that gives Dutch researchers and their collaborators access to data, resources, and services, similar to the EOOSC-EU node.